

OF ORPHANAGE HOME GUARDIANS TO OUTSIDE LIFE

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Abstract. *In this article, the results of a scientific study on the level of adaptation of children of orphanages to family life are highlighted, in which the importance of psychological characteristics of the individual in the process of organizing mutual relations in the adaptation of children is scientifically analyzed.*

Keywords: *Guardianship, adaptation, compromise, agreement.*

INCOME AND VALUE. In world educational and scientific research centers psychological features of socialization of family-type orphanage children study is being conducted. In this regard, it is necessary to determine the causes of the factors influencing the children who are deprived of parental care to find their place in social life and to be formed as full-fledged individuals, to study the problems of their socialization. It is important to study psychological factors in the socialization of family-type children, social-psychological adaptation, the role of values in their socialization, and the issues of expanding their ability to adapt to social life by changing their behavior. From this point of view, there is a need to pay special attention to the identification and research of psychological characteristics that are important in the implementation of socialization of orphanage children.

In recent years, new Uzbekistan has created the legal and regulatory framework for material and moral support of the population in need of social protection: "... to build a people-friendly state and implement a unified state policy in the field of social protection by enhancing human dignity and further developing a free civil society." the priorities of preparing children in need of social protection for independent life are gaining importance ... ». This is the psychological characteristics of the socialization of family-type orphanage children. It can be a sufficient basis for the scientific study of learning and researching the mechanism of behavior formation.

METHODS AND LEVEL OF STUDY. Today, the number of children who are deprived of parental love in the world is increasing day by day, according to world statistics, the number of such children exceeds 1 million. Looking at the statistical and scientific data, it is possible to see the following cases: the problem of neglected children during the wars in the world, the education of orphaned children is recognized as the main problem that needs attention.

In this regard, world scientists, including psychologists and pedagogues, paid special attention to this problem and conducted several researches in this regard. It is worth noting that regarding the problem of studying the psychology of children being raised in an orphanage, A.A. Vinogradova's "Pedagogical guidance in the educational process of an orphanage", M.A. Zemlyanukhina's "Communication characteristics of young children of a closed institution", A.Yu. Maroko's "Parenting Adaptation of deprived adolescents", A.A. Lyubanov's "Formation of moral relations between the children of the children's home and the teacher", S.K. Nurtasakov's "Educational work in the children's home", E.V. Nekrasova's "The self of the children of the labor correctional colony cognitive features", A.M. Prikhojan's "Research on the mental development

of small children educated in a closed children's institution", A.S. Spivakovskaya's "Psychological support for families with children raised in a state institution" should be mentioned. The research conducted by us corresponds to the period of the former Soviet Union, it is worth saying that in those times there was a small amount of research in this regard, which is to conduct research on the psychological conditions of children of family-type orphanages, their future becoming full members of society, and their socialization. cause the issue to be ignored.

Although pedagogues and psychologists around the world are conducting extensive research on this problem, they are not able to achieve positive scientific results, the reason for this is that there is a difference in the data collected based on the results of research, different theories are used in conducting scientific research, and the variety of methodologies used in research. and if it reduces the possibility of mutual comparison of the obtained results, factors such as nationality, customs, upbringing and ethnic characteristics were not taken into account in the comparative analysis of the obtained results. At the same time, it should be noted that the conducted research is in the direction of pedagogical theory.

RESEARCH RESULTS. Socialization of children of family-type orphanages, adaptation to social life (community, group, family life) is a process directly related to interpersonal relations. It is known that the manifestation of interpersonal relations at one or another level is a situation that occurs on the basis of a person's behavior, his psychological characteristics, his behavior, and the culture of behavior.

While studying the issue of socialization of foster children of family-type orphanages, we paid attention to a situation that is important in this regard, that is, we tried to study the state of their adaptability to families. For this purpose, we developed a socio-psychological questionnaire. This questionnaire consists of three questions and nine answer options. The results of the conducted research are reflected in Table 1 below.

Table 1

Results of a questionnaire to determine the level of adaptability of family-type orphanages to families

No	Survey questions	Jizzakh n = 13%	Samarkand n = 18%	Kashkadarya n = 24%
1.	Can you adopt foster children as your own?			
	a) I accept	23	22.2	16.6
	b) I try to accept	30.7	44.4	45.8
	c) it does not depend only on us	46.1	33.3	37.5
2.	Have the children in your care adapted to your family environment?			
	a) they adapted	23.0	22.2	16.6
	b) trying to adapt	30.7	38.8	37.5
	c) from that a little I'm worried	46.1	38.8	45.8
3.	What is the relationship between your children and foster children?			
	a) their relationship is good	23.0	22.2	20.8
	b) I think they will get along	30.7	33.3	37.5
	c) this situation worries us a little	46.1	44.4	10

The question of this survey is "Can you accept foster children as your own?" to the question, 16.6-23.0% of parents (guardians) of Kashkadarya, Samarkand and Jizzakh regions "accept", 30.7-45.8% "try to accept", 33.3-46.1% and those who chose the answer "it doesn't depend only on us". This situation indicates that 16.6-23.0 percent of guardians show affection to children, create all conditions for them, and love them as their own children. It was shown that 30.7-45.8 percent of guardians try to understand children's social status and show affection. The guardians who showed results of 33.3-46.1 percent stated that adaptation of children to the family does not depend only on them, this situation also depends on the character, behavior and behavior of the children, as well as their mental state. Questionnaire "Have the children in your care been able to adapt to the environment of your family?" 23.0% of the respondents from Jizzakh, 22.2% of the guardians from Samarkand, 16.6% of the guardians from Kashkadarya gave the answer "they have adapted", while the answer to the same question was "trying to adapt" was answered by 30.7% of the guardians from Jizzakh, 38% of the guardians from Samarkand .8 percent, 37.5 percent of Kashkadarya parents chose it. 46.1 % of respondents from Jizzakh , 38.8% of parents from Samarkand and 45.8% of guardians from Kashkadarya answered that they are "a little worried about this". Therefore, there is some difficulty in adapting to the family environment of children who have moved from an orphanage to a family orphanage. In this case, the custodial parents should establish mutual relations taking into account the mental state of the children, their character traits, allow them to get used to the family environment, temporarily refrain from strict control and conduct educational work.

The socio-psychological questionnaire "What is the relationship between your children and the children you take care of?" 23% of parents from Jizzakh, 22.2% of parents from Samarkand and 20.8% of parents from Kashkadarya chose the answer "good relationship". Parents from Jizzakh (30.7 percent), Samarkand (33.3 percent) and Kashkadarya (37.5 percent), Jizzakh (46.1 percent), Samarkand (44.4 percent) answered "I think they will get along." percent) and Kashkadarya (41.6 percent) parents answered that "this situation worries us a little."

CONCLUSION. The family, family environment, mutual relations between parents and children, parents' place in the family and their behavior, manifestation of character traits are of great importance in the socialization of children of family-type orphanages. From this point of view, attention should be paid to the effective organization of interactions between children in the family and children adopted into the family, the formation of a sense of mutual respect between them, cooperation, compromise, adaptation to the will, non-competition, self-control, reliance on national values, emotional stability. we think that paying attention to it will have a positive effect on their socialization and adaptation to the family environment.

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